

Synthesis, characterization and antimicrobial studies of Ti^{III}, Mn^{II}, Cu^{II} complexes with semicarbazones

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Synthesis and characterization of five Schiff bases viz. bis(cinnamaldehyde) semicarbazone (CSCZ), bis(4-chlorobenzaldehyde) semicarbazone (CBSCZ), bis(3,4,5-trimethoxybenzaldehyde) semicarbazone (TMBSCZ), bis(pyridine-2-aldehyde) semicarbazone (PASCZ), bis(thiophene-2-aldehyde) semicarbazone (TASCZ) and their complexes with Ti^{III}, Mn^{II}, Cu^{II} are being described.

Schiff bases (CSCZ), (CBSCZ), (TMBSCZ), (PASCZ), (TASCZ) were synthesised by the condensation of respective aldehyde and semicarbazide in the ratio of 2 : 1 in ethanol solutions. Metal complexes were prepared by refluxing their methanol solution for 2 h. IR, magnetic, TGA and ESR studies of the complexes indicate that the complexes have octahedral geometry. All the complexes were screened for their antimicrobial activity by agar disc diffusion method against the bacteria *X. citri* and the fungi *A. solani*.

Results and discussion

All the complexes were subjected to elemental analyses for C, H, N. These values indicate that the metal ion reacts with the ligand in the stoichiometric ratio of 1 : 2. Their molar conductance was measured in three solvents viz. CH₃OH, DMF and DMSO at 10⁻³ M dilution. The spin only values of magnetic moments indicates that all the complexes are paramagnetic in nature. The Ti^{III}, Mn^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes show μ_{eff} values in the range of 1.59–1.73, 5.85–5.92, 1.62–1.72 B.M. respectively, indicating their octahedral geometry. The electronic spectra of the Ti^{III} complexes exhibit a band at 17900 cm⁻¹. The spectrum of the complexes also show a weak band at 22525 cm⁻¹ with a shoulder in the region of 17350 cm⁻¹. These bands have been assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ transitions respectively¹. All the Mn^{II} complexes show a large number of bands in their electronic spectra around 40.00, 30.00 and 25.00 KK which are all charge transfer in nature. The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes show a broad band in the region of 13400–13600 cm⁻¹ (ϵ 1.0–11.3) characteristic of distorted octahedral structure.

The IR spectra of the ligands and their complexes have been discussed in detail^{2,4}. The most important band occurs in all the Schiff bases is for the ν C=N stretching (1590–1640 cm⁻¹). These shifts in C=N stretching suggest that the nitrogen of the azomethine group is coordinated to metal ion. The IR spectra of the complexes show a new band at 3350 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to ν OH stretching vibrations⁵. TGA results support the inference drawn by IR spectra regarding the presence of coordinated water molecules. Agar disc diffusion method was used for antimicrobial activity. All the complexes and ligands were found to be highly active against the fungi and bacteria. The growth inhibition capacity of all the complexes was found in the order : Cu^{II} > Mn^{II} > Ti^{III}.

	Compound (concn. 0.1%)	% Inhibition	
		<i>X. citri</i>	<i>A. solani</i>
1	[Cu(C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O) ₂ .2H ₂ O]SO ₄	67.01	62.43
2	[Cu(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ OCl ₂) ₂ .2H ₂ O]SO ₄	96.28	88.51
3	[Cu(C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₃ O) ₂ .2H ₂ O]SO ₄	78.20	73.90
4	[Cu(C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₅ O) ₂ .2H ₂ O]SO ₄	73.92	68.00
5	[Cu(C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ OS ₂) ₂ .2H ₂ O]SO ₄	71.62	65.02
6	[Mn(C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O) ₂ .2H ₂ O]Cl ₂	58.91	46.24
7	[Mn(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ OCl ₂) ₂ .2H ₂ O]Cl ₂	91.37	84.00
8	[Mn(C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₃ O) ₂ .2H ₂ O]Cl ₂	71.02	60.35
9	[Mn(C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₅ O) ₂ .2H ₂ O]Cl ₂	60.24	63.30
10	[Mn(C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ OS ₂) ₂ .2H ₂ O]Cl ₂	63.07	61.08
11	[Ti(C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O) ₂ .2H ₂ O]Cl ₃	52.78	50.91
12	[Ti(C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₃ OCl ₂) ₂ .2H ₂ O]Cl ₃	88.07	79.52
13	[Ti(C ₂₁ H ₂₅ N ₃ O) ₂ .2H ₂ O]Cl ₃	68.17	63.08
14	[Ti(C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₅ O) ₂ .2H ₂ O]Cl ₃	59.03	60.08
15	[Ti(C ₁₁ H ₉ N ₃ OS ₂) ₂ .2H ₂ O]Cl ₃	62.64	60.35

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